

A Scoping Review on Sorghum Silage Quality Enhancement with Advanced Ensiling Operations

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ABSTRACT

Adequate animal nutrition is one of the vital prerequisites to enhance the productivity and performance of ruminants in terms of milk and meat production. Fodders preserved as silage have the potential to supply animal feed even during months of scorching heat of sun. Silage is preserved fodder produced in an anaerobic condition by the fermentation process in specialized air tight structures called silos. Properly prepared silage usually has equivalent or even higher nutritional value of the original fodder. Forage sorghum has been found to be excellent choice for silage making as it gives a comparatively higher tonnage of green forage yield on per hectare basis and it uses only one third of nitrogen and water than that of forage maize. Proper moisture, plant sugar levels, anaerobic conditions and bacterial cultures for fermentation process are the basic elements of silage making. Chop length, plant moisture, sugar levels and silage inoculants are some of the factors that influence the quality of sorghum silage. Prussic acid and nitrate toxicity are potentially harmful compounds which may deteriorate silage quality and may even leads to animal death. To avoid prussic acid and nitrate accumulation, sorghum should never be harvested immediately after drought, prolonged cloudy conditions, frost and in cool temperatures after hotter ones. In this way, high quality sorghum silage can go a long way in increasing the productivity of milch animals and can play its due role in ensuring the food security of teeming millions across the globe.

Key words: Anaerobic fermentation, Animal nutrition, Fodder preservation, Nitrate toxicity, Prussic acid management

INTRODUCTION

Milk and meat are some of the most valued products for human beings produced by ruminant livestock [1]. Adequate animal nutrition is one of the most important factors which determine not only the quantity but the quality of the milk and meat produced. Forages and fodders have attained a special status as animal feed resource for being nutritious, economical and they have other associated advantages like ease of growing and feeding [2]. Among forages, sorghum has recently attained attention of researchers, dairy farmers and growers because of numerous advantages that it has to offer to growers and dairy farmers over other cereal forages [3]. Sorghum offers a diversity of management options making it suitable for almost all types of cropping patterns. It gives a fairly high tonnage of green forage with fewer uses of nutrients and irrigations. It has been found to be perfect for dry land, limited and full irrigation situations. It continues to supply forage of excellent nutritional quality even during months of extreme heat in tropical and subtropical regions [4]. Sorghum serves as excellent early maturing catch crop following a primary crop loss. It has been found to be a robust cover crop with outstanding rotational crop benefits [5]. Regardless of the production systems, the adaptive nature of sorghum, its potential to produce higher tonnage of green forage and its diverse uses make it a valued tool and one of the best choices for forage growers and dairy farmers demanding high quality feed stocks. Last but not least, sorghum is one of the best fodder crops for silage making. In the simplest

terms, silage is the fermented feed prepared in anaerobic conditions having comparable or even higher quality attributes than green forage [6]. Carefully prepared sorghum silage continues to supply nutritious feed to ruminant livestock even during the peak of summer months when other green forages go out of scene. Thus silage can be declared without any shadow of a doubt as one of the most valued inventions of the century made in the fields of dairy farming and animal nutrition [7]. Silage making techniques have been continuously gone under rigorous testing and consequently a variety of improvements have been suggested. Recent advances have made it possible to prepare silage in diverse climatic conditions and low technological level. However, basic principles of silage making techniques remain the same and if followed in true sense then sorghum silage has the potential to bridge the gap between animal feed supply and demand particularly during summer months [8].

The objectives and aims of this scoping review are to highlight the recent advances made in silage making techniques particularly in reference with sorghum silage. This paper brings into light various agronomic management techniques of sorghum fodder for better quality silage production. In the end, the latest advances to prevent the production of harmful compounds in sorghum silage are discussed.

Types of Sorghum

Forage sorghum, sudangrass and sorghum-sudangrass are three classes of sorghum which are generally used for forage [7]. As characteristics differ both across and within these different

types of sorghums used for forage, thus each class offers a multiple-use opportunities and uses to growers. Among these types, forage sorghums are generally taller and tend to produce more leaves. Forage sorghums are late maturing in comparison with grain sorghums. Another characteristic which differentiates forage sorghum from grain sorghum is the development of the comparatively smaller head by forage sorghums as compared to grain types. Forage sorghums have sweet stalks which increases their palatability to livestock when fed either as green roughage or as hay. The greatest advantage associated with forage sorghums is their potential to produce higher tonnage of green forage per unit of the area and time [9]. However, forage sorghums have limited regrowth potential making them the best choice as a single-cut silage crop and/or green-chop production uses. The harvesting stage of forage sorghums is one of the most important factors which determine their quality and thus the soft dough stage has been found to be the most appropriate stage for most of the forage sorghums. Forage sorghums are the best choice for silage preparation as compared to other sorghums. Sudangrass is another type of sorghum with similar plant architecture except it develops multiple tillers and has finer stalks. As compared to forage or grain sorghums, it looks more like a grass plant [10]. Another difference of sudangrass from forage sorghum is its excellent regrowth ability as it recovers quickly after harvesting. However, it produces comparatively less biomass tonnage per single harvest than forage sorghums. Sudangrass is most suited for grazing as well as hay production [11]. It is also known to be a good cover crop. Sorghum-sudangrass hybrids, also known by the name of haygrazer, are typically crosses between female parents of forage sorghum and male parent of sudangrass types [12]. These produce more tonnage than sudangrass because of strong tillering habit. These have higher potential for regrowth than forage sorghum but lesser than sudangrass [13]. However these are considered to be a well suited option for multiple harvest systems [14]. Sorghum-sudangrass hybrids are excellent choice for grazing and hay production [15]. It can also be used for silage preparation, however, sorghum-sudangrass hybrids require more time for wilting due to higher moisture contents [16, 17, 18]. Among all these sorghums, forage sorghum types have been found to be more suitable for silage making.

Four basic elements of silage fermentation

The fermentation process which preserves fodders as silage is actually biochemistry in action. Successful completion of silage fermentation requires four basic elements without which the fermentation process gets disrupted and resultantly quality of silage takes nose dive. The first and foremost element is the provision of anaerobic conditions since fermentation requires no oxygen at all. Oxygen is considered to be the worst enemy of silage during the fermentation process [19]. Anaerobic conditions are developed because cells of sorghum plants are still metabolically active and these active cells in conjunction with some microorganisms produce heat and carbon dioxide. Anaerobic conditions develop with the rise of CO₂ level [20]. Fermentation gets started when the respiration ceases. If CO₂ is finding a way to escape or if there is too much air present, then respiration will continue and plant materials continue to use sugars. Therefore, it is important to pack and cover the chopped materials as soon as soon possible. Chopped forage is compressed in order to remove the air while ensiling. The

optimum moisture level of the sorghum needs to be ensured before chopping and that level is between the ranges of 60-70% [21]. Adequate sugar levels need to be maintained in order to provide source of energy for bacteria during the fermentation process. Deficiency of sugars usually results in production of harmful substances. Last but not least is the provision of proper bacteria to drive the anaerobic process [22]. During the anaerobic process acetic acid and lactic acids are produced when the respiration process stops by anaerobic bacteria which feed on sugars present in chopped plant materials. Fermentation process is slowed down with the production of lactic acid until it stops due to higher concentration of acids. Another important factor that needs to be kept in consideration is the pH of 4.2 that must be attained during the first three weeks.

Silage making operations influencing the quality of silage

A variety of factors influence silage quality and if managed properly can result in improved quality of sorghum silage. The first and foremost factor that needs to be kept into consideration during ensiling is the chop length of forage sorghum because it affects the packing process in silos. It has been found that finely cut and chopped sorghum gets compacted easily than longer cut/chopped sorghum. Some modern harvesters have the capacity to cut sorghum as small as 0.25 inches [23]. Finely chopped sorghum not only makes the packing process easy but it also effects animal intake. It has been found that short chop length resulted in significantly higher intake by ruminant livestock. Some other researchers have found that a chop length of 1.25 inches of sorghum fodder as an optimum chop length. Longer chop length than 1.25 inches [24] results in hindrance during compaction process of chopped materials but also reduces intake by dairy animals. Another important factor which can improve the quality of sorghum silage is adequate compaction of chopped forage sorghum material. Compaction removes air and without which remaining air will cause a different type of fermentation in which there will be more respiration and resultantly over heating will deteriorate the silage quality. Therefore it is recommended that rate/speed of chopping should never be more than the speed of compaction. Adequate compaction is characterized by the factor that in case of proper compaction, chopped material should be difficult to dig out with bare hands. Inadequate compaction results in overheating and resultantly it leads to a silage of much darker color with a distinct caramel smell. It has been found that the nutritional quality of overheated silage is very low. The moisture level of ensiling material also affects the quality of sorghum silage. It is recommended that it should be in the range of 60-70% depending upon the method of storage. Higher moisture contents of chopped materials result in the loss of precious nutrients which are soluble and get deposited at the bottom of the bunker or storage facility/silo as silage effluent. Moisture level can be checked by taking plant samples, chopping them and noting its fresh weigh. Then these samples are oven dried to record their dry weights. The difference between fresh and dry weights gives the moisture percentage. If the moisture level is more than 70%, then sorghum can be harvested but should be allowed to dry and wilt in field. It should also be noted that if the moisture contents are below than 60%, then compaction of the chopped materials will be difficult [25]. Sufficient plant sugars also ensure good quality of sorghum silage because these are necessary for the production

of lactic acid. Deficiency of sugars results in the production of butyric acid instead of lactic acid. The harvesting stage influences sugar levels in forage sorghum, so if sorghum is harvested at the appropriate growth stage, plant sugars are not a serious problem in sorghum. It has been found that sorghum harvesting at 1-2 weeks after flowering depending upon early or late maturing cultivars gives the best results as far as sorghum silage is concerned. Silage inoculants which are the bacterial cultures have the potential to improve the quality of sorghum silage. The silage inoculant aid in lactic acid fermentation and resultantly good quality silage is produced. It is interesting to note that though lactic acid bacteria occur naturally but the addition of silage inoculants expedites the fermentation process. It is also worthy to mention that finished silage product should be same or higher in quality as that of green forage of sorghum. Digestibility, energy and protein are some of the parameters to determine the quality of sorghum silage.

Prussic acid poisoning and its management

Prussic acid and nitrates are potentially harmful compounds which can deteriorate the quality of sorghum silage. Sorghum contains a molecule having both carbohydrate and non-carbohydrate portions in same molecule called cyanogenic glycoside [26]. This molecule breaks down after hydrolysis (chemical process of water addition) carbohydrate and non-carbohydrate segments. The non-carbohydrate portion/cyanide becomes hydrocyanic acid as a result of decomposition process. Hydrocyanic acid is commonly known by the name of prussic acid or dhurrin. The mechanism involved in prussic acid formation is very interesting and needs to be understood in order to prevent its formation. The cyanogenic compounds are produced in epidermal cells which are the outer layers of cells, while the enzymes which catalyze the formation of these compounds are located in mesophyll cells or leaf tissue cells. Whenever plant tissue gets damaged by chopping, cutting, chewing, trampling, then enzymes come in contact with cyanogenic compounds and resultantly the prussic acid is formed. When forage sorghum plants or chopped materials containing prussic acid are fed to livestock; these are dissolved in the blood and are transported throughout the body of the animal through its blood stream. Prussic acid has been found to restrict the utilization of oxygen in the animal's body. Forage sorghum has been reported to have high concentration of prussic acid at young rapidly growing stages. Rainfall or heavy irrigation after drought also causes production of prussic acid in higher quantities. A reasonably cool temperature after warm temperature also causes forage sorghum to produce more prussic acid at any growth stage [27]. There are several other factors which cause elevation in the production of prussic acid in forage sorghum such as resumed growth of forage sorghum after mild to severe drought, frost, higher nitrogen levels in soil, considerably lower phosphorous levels in soil profile and last but not least is the application of 2,4-D herbicide. The harmful effects of prussic acid can be avoided by virtually lowering its production by adopting and applying latest advances in the production of forage sorghum and its silage. Forage sorghum should never be harvested for chopping or preservation as silage when it has resumed growth after drought or freezing/frost like conditions [28]. No ensiling operation has been found to be effective in reducing the concentration of

prussic acid in chopped materials of sorghum, however it has been found that if little time is offered between sorghum harvesting and its preservation as silage then prussic acid gets volatilized in comparatively fewer quantities. The reduction of prussic acid can be achieved if sorghum is harvested and directly moved to a storage facility. In contrast if sorghum is allowed to wilt before chopping and ensiling then prussic acid has enough time to be released and volatilized. It is suggested that if prussic acid presence is suspected then do not feed the silage for 3-4 weeks to allow time for dissipation.

Nitrate toxicity management

Nitrate is absorbed from the soil solution by the plants and gets converted into amino acids which are the building blocks of protein. Nitrate assimilation requires water, energy and optimum temperature, however in the wake of drought or any other stress, the assimilation process gets disrupted and nitrate starts to accumulate in leaves and lower third of sorghum stalks. Thus sorghum may tend to accumulate nitrates at any growth stage whenever growth gets disrupted by drought, frost, prolonged cloudy conditions or any other stress. Drought has been found to be the main culprit for prussic acid formation as well as nitrate accumulation in sorghum, sunflower and in maize to some extent [29]. Another phenomenon called luxury consumption can also cause nitrate toxicity in forage sorghum and this phenomenon comes into action whenever high levels of nitrogen are present in the soil. Heavy doses of nitrogen fertilizers can lead to high levels of nitrogen in the soil. Addition of organic manures may also lead to nitrate toxicity due to a sudden release of nitrogen in short span of time instead of a slow releasing of nutrients. Unlike of prussic acid, nitrate gets affected by fermentation process as 50% of nitrates are converted to non-toxic compounds. It has been found that silage with high nitrate levels may be fed to animals if mixed with other forages or supplementing it with some other grains. It is advised that such silage must not be fed to hungry, pregnant or stressed animals. It is worth mentioning that nitrate toxicity is actually a common term but the actual harmful compound for ruminants is nitrite. Nitrate gets converted into nitrite in the rumen and then absorbed into the blood stream from the walls of rumen. Nitrite is the biggest enemy of oxygen carrying molecule in blood called hemoglobin which is converted into methahemoglobin. The net result is animal's death due to deficiency of oxygen (asphyxiation) as methahemoglobin cannot transport oxygen as that of hemoglobin. The normal bright red color of blood is maintained by hemoglobin but due to presence of methahemoglobin, it turns into a brown color [30]. Both prussic acid and nitrate toxicity can be avoided if harvesting is delayed for 1-3 weeks in the wake of rain after a medium to severe drought. Another technique can reduce nitrate concentration in the chopped materials if sorghum is harvested at a higher stubble height because nitrates get accumulated in the lower portion of the sorghum stalks. Potassium application has also been found to be effective in mitigating the drastic effects of unused nitrogen in forage sorghum.

Limitations of sorghum as a silage crop

Sorghum is an excellent crop for silage preparation particularly if silage additives such as sugar cane or sugar beet molasses are added to improve the quality of the silage. If sorghum is grown in intercropping systems with legumes, then not only green

forage yield gets enhances but quality of green forage also improves because legumes are a rich source of protein. However there are some challenges regarding sorghum silage preparation that need attention to make sorghum silage with higher digestibility values. Small coarse grains like sorghum are difficult to crack or break down and these remain intact. Even after the animal's intake, sorghum remains are not digested in rumen and as a result are passed on in an intact form. Comparatively, larger grains like maize are easier to break down than sorghum grains. Thus this factor needs to be paid attention to and some sort of technique needs to be evolved to break down sorghum grains in order to increase the digestibility of sorghum silage.

CONCLUSION

Forage sorghum not only yields higher green forage tonnage on a per hectare basis, but it has the potential to give excellent silage if prepared with care on a scientific basis. Silage of sorghum requires four basic elements including anaerobic conditions, proper moisture and sugar levels along with sufficient bacterial population to carry on the fermentation process. Other factors such as the harvesting stage of the sorghum, chop length, type of silos and silage additives such as molasses also affect the digestibility, palatability and protein contents of silage. Prussic acid and nitrate toxicity management with advanced agronomic and plant nutrient management as well as adoption of advanced ensiling operations has the potential to improve the silage quality by reducing the concentration of potentially harmful compounds in sorghum silage.

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REFERENCES

1. Iqbal, M.A. 2015. Agronomic management strategies elevate forage sorghum yield: A Review. *J. Adv. Bot. Zool.*, 3(2): 1-6.
2. Iqbal, M.A., A. Iqbal, N. Akbar, H.Z. Khan and R.N. Abbas, 2015. A study on feed stuffs role in enhancing the productivity of milch animals in Pakistan- Existing scenario and future prospect. *Global Veterinaria*, 14(1): 23-33.
3. Iqbal, M.A. and A. Iqbal. 2015. Overviewing forage shortage for dairy animals and suitability of forage sorghum for ensiling. *Global Veterinaria*, 14(2): 173-177.
4. Iqbal, M.A., B. Ahamd, M.H. Shah and K. Ali, 2015. A study on forage sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) production in perspectives of white revolution in Punjab, Pakistan: Issues and future options. *American-Eurasian J. Agric. Environ. Sci.*, 15 (4): 640-647.
5. Iqbal, M.A., A.M. Saleem and B. Ahmad, 2015. Effect of seed invigoration techniques on germination and seedling growth of Chinese sweet sorghum. *J. Adv. Bot. Zool.*, 2(2): 1-4.
6. Hussain, I., S.A. Jatoti, O. Sayal and M.S. Baloch, 2002. Green fodder yield and land equivalent ratio of

- sorghum-legume association. *Pak. J. Biol. Sci.*, 3(1):175-176.
7. Undersander, D.J., L.H. Smith, A.R. Kaminski, K.A. Kelling and J.D. Doll, 1990. Forage sorghum. On-line retrieved on 15-05-2015 from <http://corn.agronomy.wisc.edu/Crops/SorghumForage.aspx>.
8. Oliver, A.L., R.J. Grant, J.F. Pedersen and J. Orear. 2004. Comparison of brown midrib-6 and-18 forage sorghum with conventional sorghum and corn silage in diets of lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 87(3): 637-644.
9. Meeske, Robin, G. Ashbell, Z.G. Weinberg and T. Kipnis. Ensiling forage sorghum at two stages of maturity with the addition of lactic acid bacterial inoculants. *Animal Feed Sci. Technol.*, 43(3): 165-175.
10. Casler, M.D., J.F. Pedersen and D.J. Undersander. 2003. Forage yield and economic losses associated with the brown-midrib trait in sudangrass. *Crop Sci.*, 43(3): 782-789.
11. Mohammed, M.I. 2010. New Sudangrass forage cultivars selected from the original population (*Sorghum bicolor* 'Garawi', syn. *S. sudanense*). *Afri. J. Range Forage Sci.*, 27(1): 51-55.
12. Pratt, P.F., S. Davis, R.G. Sharpless, W.J. Pugh and S.E. Bishop. 1976. Nitrate contents of Sudangrass and barley forages grown on plots treated with animal manures. *Agron. J.* 68(2): 311-314.
13. Venuto, Brad and B. Kindiger. 2008. Forage and biomass feedstock production from hybrid forage sorghum and sorghum-sudangrass hybrids. *Grassland sci.*, 54(4): 189-196.
14. Pedersen, J.F. and J.J. Toy. 1997. Forage yield, quality, and fertility of sorghum× sudan grass hybrids in A1 and A3 cytoplasm. *Crop sci.*, 37(6): 1973-1975.
15. Tew, T.L. R.M. Cobill and E.P. Richard. 2008. Evaluation of sweet sorghum and sorghum× sudangrass hybrids as feedstocks for ethanol production. *Bioenergy Res.*, 1(2): 147-152.
16. Clapp, J.G. and D.S. Chamblee. 1970. Influence of different defoliation systems on the regrowth of pearl millet, hybrid sudangrass and two sorghum-sudangrass hybrids from terminal, axillary, and basal buds. *Crop Sci.*, 10(4): 345-349.
17. Forney, D.R. and C.L. Foy. 1985. Phytotoxicity of products from rhizospheres of a sorghum-sudangrass hybrid (*Sorghum bicolor*× *Sorghum sudanense*). *Weed Sci.*, 597-604.
18. Ferreira, P.D.S., L.C. Gonçalves, J.A.S. Rodrigues, D.G. Jayme, E. Saliba, O. Neto, D.S.G. Cruz, F.A. Magalhães, G. de O. Ribeiro Junior and F.O. Velasco. 2015. Nutritional value of sorghum-sudangrass hybrids (*Sorghum bicolor*× *Sorghum sudanense*) harvested at different stages of maturity." *Semina: Ciências Agrárias (Londrina)* 36(1): 377-390.
19. Colombini, S., M. Zucali, L. Rapetti, G.M. Crovetto, A. Sandrucci and L. Bava. 2015. Substitution of corn silage with sorghum silages in lactating cow diets: In vivo methane emission and global warming potential of milk production. *Agric. Sys.*, 136: 106-113.

20. Zegada-Lizarazu, W. and A. Monti. 2015. An integrated approach to harvest and storage of sweet sorghum at farm scale. *Bio Energy Res.*, 8(1): 450-458.
21. Iqbal, M.A., A. Iqbal, K. Ali, H. Ali, R.D. Khan, Ahmad, B. F. Nabeel and A. Raza. 2015. Integration of forage sorghum and by-products of sugarcane and sugar beet industries for ruminant nutrition: A Review. *Global Veterinaria*, 14(5): 752-760.
22. Nishino, N., Y. Ogata, H. Han and Y. Yamamoto. 2015. Identification of bacteria in total mixed ration silage produced with and without crop silage as an ingredient. *Animal Sci. J.*, 86(1): 45-50.
23. Neves, A.L.A., R.D. Santos, L.G.R. Pereira, G.F. Oliveira, C.B. Scherer, R.S. Verneque, and T. Mcallister. 2015. Agronomic characteristics, silage quality, intake and digestibility of five new Brazilian sorghum cultivars. *The J. Agric. Sci.*, 153(2): 371-380.
24. Jian, G., Y. Cuijun, and L. Guihe. 2015. Nutritional Evaluation of Fresh and Wilted Mixed Silage of Naked Oats (*Avena nuda*) and Alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*). *Int. J. Agric. Biol.* 17(4): 23-35.
25. Zhang, S., AS. Chaudhry, A. Osman, C. Shi, G.R. Edwards, R.J. Dewhurst and L. Cheng. 2015. Associative effects of ensiling mixtures of sweet sorghum and alfalfa on nutritive value, fermentation and methane characteristics. *Animal Feed Sci. Technol.*, 206: 29-38.
26. Ahmed, E.A. 2015. Evaluation of the performance of seven forage sorghum (sorghum species) in Khartoum State, Sudan (Doctoral dissertation, UOFK).
27. Seglar, W.J. and R.D. Shaver. 2014. Management and assessment of ensiled forages and high-moisture grain. *Veterinary Clinics of North America: Food Animal Practice* 30(3): 507-538.
28. Kamra, D.N., N. Agarwal and L.C. Chaudhary. 2015. Nitrate/nitrite toxicity and possibilities of their use in ruminant diet. In *rumen microbiology: From evolution to revolution*. Springer India. pp. 343-347.
29. Khanum Al Akbari, W.M. and S. Umar. 2014. Potassium fertilization-an effective mitigator of unused nitrogen in forage sorghum. *J. Plant Biochem. Physiol.*, 2: 126-134.
30. Singh, J., J.S. Hundal, H.K. Verma and S.K. Kansal. 2014. Awareness among dairy farmers of Punjab about common toxicities in ruminants. *Haryana Veterinarian*, 53(2): 130-132.

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